

tion of the ascorbic acid and INH contents of commercial pharmaceutical preparations as per the following procedure. One tablet of the preparation was ground into a fine powder, dissolved in deionised water, filtered through a G4 sintered glass funnel, washed and the filtrate diluted to 100 ml. In the case of ascorbic acid, a known volume of the solution was treated with 0.1 M KBr solution (1 ml) and a 0.1% solution (0.1 ml) of PS, MV, AV, ST, WFBBL or AS, diluted to 50 ml, and the mixture titrated with 0.1 N CAT solution until the colour changes mentioned in Table 1 were obtained. A similar aliquot was titrated with CAT solution using starch as indicator² for the sake of comparison. The procedure was repeated with different commercial samples of vitamin C tablets. The results obtained are in very good agreement with those obtained with starch as indicator.

In the case of INH, an aliquot of the solution prepared from the tablet, was treated with enough 1:1 HCl to give an overall acidity of 1 M when diluted to 50 ml, and one drop of 0.1% ST, WFBBL or AS, and the mixture was titrated with 0.1 N CAT solution till the colour changes mentioned in Table 1 were obtained. The results obtained are in very good agreement with those obtained with quinoline yellow as indicator³.

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Emission Spectrographic Estimation of Silver, Bismuth, Molybdenum and Vanadium in Soil and Rocks

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An emission spectrographic procedure is described for the estimation of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in parts per billion levels in soils and rocks. The sample is attacked by aqua regia and the above elements are adsorbed on activated charcoal, which is ashed, and the four elements are estimated by measuring their respective spectral intensities.

Experimental

Preparation of samples: The sample (10 g) powdered to 200 mesh was spread evenly in a flat-

bottomed (3" dia) porcelain dish and roasted in a muffle furnace at 400° for 1 h. It was cooled, transferred to a 400 ml beaker and freshly prepared aqua regia (20 ml) was added. The sample was then digested for 4–5 h on a water-bath with stirring, and demineralised water (250 ml) was added, stirred well, and left overnight. The solution was filtered through Whatman no. 40 filter paper into a 500 ml beaker and the residue on the filter paper was washed 4–5 times with demineralised water, making sure that no residue passed into the filtrate. The filtrate was diluted to 400 ml with demineralised water. Into the filtrate, A.R. quality activated charcoal (0.5 g of 200 mesh) was added and stirred for 20 min with a magnetic stirrer. The solution was then filtered through a Whatman no. 41 filter paper and the filtrate rejected. The filter paper containing the charcoal was carefully placed in a 30 ml flat-bottomed porcelain crucible and kept in a muffle furnace. The temperature of the furnace was slowly raised to 550° and maintained for ~1.5 h till the contents of the crucible were completely converted into ash. Access to air should be allowed during the ashing of the charcoal in the muffle furnace.

Preparation of standards: Specpure samples of oxides of Ag, Bi, Mo and V were weighed and mixed thoroughly in an agate pestle and mortar with a pegmatite base (I) so as to make a final concentration of 1000 ppm of each element. Pegmatite base was prepared by mixing together 60 parts of 200 mesh quartz (specpure) with 40 parts of 200 mesh spectrographically screened microcline and 1 part of iron oxide (specpure). Further dilutions of the standard were made with pegmatite base as per Table 1, so as to form

TABLE 1—DILUTIONS MADE TO PREPARE STANDARD SOLID SOLUTIONS

Content of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in the initial solid solution	Quantity of the initial solution taken	Quantity of Pegmatite base mixed	Final quantity of the solid solution	Ag, Bi, Mo and V content in the final solid solution
1000	1.0	9.0	10.0	100
100	1.0	9.0	10.0	10
10	1.0	9.0	10.0	1
1.0	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.1
0.1	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.01
0.01	1.0	9.0	10.0	0.001

a series of standard solid solutions with concentrations of 100, 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01 and 0.001 ppm. Each standard was thoroughly mixed to make sure the homogeneity of the sample. Each standard (10 g) was weighed into a 250 ml beaker and aqua regia (20 ml) added. All the steps adopted for the samples were followed for the standards to obtain the spectrum of the four elements. By a visual comparison of the intensity of the spectrum of the four elements in the unknown sample with

TABLE 2—RESULTS OBTAINED USING INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

Name of International standards used	Values obtained by the present method (ppm)				Recommended values (ppm)			
	Ag	Bi	Mo	V	Ag	Bi	Mo	V
Soil SO-4	0.001-0.01	0.01-0.1	0.1-1.0	10-100	n.i.	0.1	1.0	90 ^a
Peridotite PCC-1	0.001-0.01	0.01-0.1	0.1-1.0	10-100	0.005	0.013	0.2	30 ^b
Gabbro MRG-1	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	1.0-10	>100	0.14	n.i.	n.i.	520 ^c

n.r. = Not reported. ^aRef. 2. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 4.

that of the known standards, the amount of the four elements in the unknown was easily obtained.

Instrumentation: Into the crucible containing the ash, the flux (15 mg) containing Sp-2 graphite powder and lithium carbonate (A.R) in the proportion of 1:1 were added, and was transferred completely to a small agate mortar (50 mm dia) with the help of a brush and ground well with agate pestle. The whole mass was then transferred to the crater of a graphite electrode with the help of a funnel and weighing paper. The electrode (4.57 mm dia) used was of Union Carbide make. The crater was of 8 mm depth and 3.2 mm dia. The crater containing the sample was kept under i.r. lamp for an hour and arced using a counter electrode of 3.04 mm dia and coned to 60°.

The arcing was carried out in a 1.5 Meter Wadsworth Spectrograph (Jarrel-Ash) at a current of 10 A dc for 60 s. The arcing gap was adjusted 3 mm throughout and slit width used was 10 microns. Development and fixing of the spectrum was done for 3 min at 72°F using Kodak developer and fixer. Stop bath was used for 30 s at 72°F. Drying of the film was carried out in an automatic photoprocessor.

Results and Discussion

Silver was estimated by studying its spectral intensity at 3280.683 Å, bismuth at 3067.716 Å, molybdenum at 3170.347 Å and vanadium at 3185.396 Å. The results of analysis are those values which lie between two adjacent values of the standards.

International standards have been analysed by this procedure and the results obtained were found very satisfactory. The results are shown in Table 2. The procedure has been found to be accurate for estimation of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in parts per billion levels, and is less costly.

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Naphthalein Scarlet-4RS—an Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Rare Earths

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NAPHTHALEIN scarlet-4RS a metallochromic indicator has been known to form complexes with transition metals and rare earths¹. The dye produces a blood red colour in acidic medium which makes it useful as a spectrophotometric reagent for the estimation of various metal ions. In continuation of the work in our laboratory on the trace estimation of transition metals and rare earths²⁻⁶ using amperometric titration technique, the present paper discusses a procedure for the estimation of rare earths with naphthalein scarlet-4RS, using a d m.e.—Hg pool electrode system.

Experimental

Solutions of trivalent rare earths (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Eu, Er, Tb, Dy) were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the rare earth (oxides/nitrates) in a calculated amount of perchloric acid/water and standardised⁷. The solution of naphthalein scarlet-4RS was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the reagent in conductivity water. Amperometric titrations were done on a manually operated polarograph with a multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} A/div.) using d m.e. as an indicator electrode and Hg-pool as reference electrode, the capillary characteristics in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KCl being $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$. The amperometric titrations were performed at room temperature